

Polyester Resins for Advanced Composites

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ABSTRACT

A comparison is made of engineering properties collected on various filament wound advanced composite systems. The systems studied include S-glass and AS graphite composites using both epoxy and polyester resins. The resins chosen are typical of those currently being used in structural applications. Baseline data on E-glass composites using the same resin systems are included for comparison purposes. The composite data was collected on both unidirectional and helical wound cylinders. It includes hoop tension by internal pressure, axial tension, axial compression, torsional measurements and elastic constants. The resin data was collected on plate castings and includes mechanical properties, elastic constants and thermal properties. All data is presented in a format suitable for computer calculation of composite material properties. Conclusions are developed concerning the use of polyester resin systems for advanced composite applications.

